

Table 2. Grain quality character of Mahi Sugandha and Basmati 370.

Character	Mahi Sugandha	Basmati 370
Hulling (%)	79.9	79.0
Milling (%)	69.4	64.5
Head rice recovery (%)	50.2	39.2
L/B ratio	3.34	3.48
Classification	Long, slender	Long, slender
Grain length (mm)	5.7	6.2
Length of cooked rice (mm)	10.2	10.8
Kernel color	White	White
Kernel elongation ratio	1.8	1.6
Water uptake	355	300
Volume expansion	2.0	3.2
Alkali value	6.0	5.0
Amylose (%)	27.0	22.3
Test weight (g)	20.5	21.2
Aroma	Strong	Strong
Abdominal white	Absent	Occasionally present

yielded 57.8% more than Basmati 370, which averaged 3.0 t/ha at four locations.

Mahi Sugandha came from BK79/Basmati 370. It matures in 130-135 d from seed and possesses ideal plant type with upright leaves, synchronized tillering, and late leaf senescence. Panicles are fully exerted and compact. They have long, slender, straw-colored grains that are free from abdominal white and strongly scented like Basmati 370 (Table 2). □

Ptb 45 (Matta Triveni), a promising rice variety for dry season in Kerala, India

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Farmers in Kerala prefer high-yielding, short-duration rice varieties for the dry season (Dec/Jan to Apr/May) to allow for timely planting of the succeeding monsoon crop. Annapoorna (90-100 d) has been the most popular variety cultivated.

A short-duration (100 d) rice variety Ptb 45 (Matta Triveni) was recently released by the Agricultural Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala. The pureline

Grain yield at different locations in 1988 and 1989 dry seasons.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)						
	1988			1989			
	Kodakara	Annamanada	Pananchery	Overall	Annamanada	Pananchery	Overall
Matta Triveni	3.4	4.7	3.2	3.8	3.7	3.5	3.6
Annapoorna	2.1	4.1	2.8	3.0	3.2	2.8	3.0
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	0.2		0.3	0.2	

selection from Triveni (a white bran variety) is semital with long, compact, and exerted panicles and red, medium-bold grains.

Ptb 45 was compared with Annapoorna under transplanted conditions in different irrigated farming situations in Kerala's central region during DS 1988 and 1989.

Matta Triveni consistently outyielded Annapoorna at all locations in both years (see table). Matta Triveni averaged 3.7 t grain/ha compared with 3 t/ha for Annapoorna.

Although the variety is reported to be susceptible to blast and sheath blight, incidence was less in Matta Triveni than in Annapoorna in the trials. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

BR319-1-HR38 and IR74 released as *gogorancah* varieties in Indonesia

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Gogorancah is a direct seeded rice culture for dryland conditions that also are flooded by maximum tillering stage. It was developed in rainfed areas using early-maturing lowland rice varieties, such as IR36 and Cisokan.

We conducted yield trials laid out in randomized complete block design with

Table 1. Yield performance of Cenranae (BR319-1-HR38) and IR74 on gogorancah culture. MORIF, Indonesia.

Trials	Grain yield (t/ha)				Cenranae increase (%) over		IR74 increase (%) over	
	Cenranae	IR74	GH-GRM-7	IR21178-39-PI	Cisokan	Cikapundung	Cisokan	Cikapundung
MORIF farm research (1986-89)	6.0	6.0	5.4	4.7	20	22	16	18
Multilocation trials (1987-89)	4.7	4.1	4.2	3.3	38	51	21	32
Adaptive research trial at Sidondo, Central Sulawesi (1988-89)	5.2	4.3	4.1	4.2	44	49	19	23
Adaptive research trial at East Nusatenggara (1988-89)	4.1	4.2	4.2	4.2	24	21	27	23
Adaptive research trial at Wawotobi, Southeast Sulawesi (1988-89)	5.3	4.7	4.7	4.4	23	26	9	12